

**Methods for solving simple text problems in elementary grades.
(in 4th grade)**

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Annotation: Text tasks are very important in elementary grades. Problems are very useful for the development and thinking of students. Any questions that are interesting and engage the student in thought will have a more positive impact on their brain activity. For elementary school students, not too difficult one- or two-step tasks are recommended. Through them, the horizons of thinking expand and serve as the basis for complex issues that will be worked on in the next stages. To complete any complex examples and problems, you must first be able to work with simple-looking examples and problems.

Keywords: Simple problems, addition problems, subtraction problems, double action problems, multiplication problems, division problems.

Mathematics is a world-class subject that forms the basis for the study of all subjects. The need was emphasized to increase interest in mathematics among young people, to select talented children and organize them in specialized schools, and then in higher educational institutions. The task was to create popular textbooks and teaching aids for children on this topic, written in a simple and understandable language, to form, if necessary, a mathematical mindset, starting from kindergarten.

Mathematics is the basis of all exact sciences. A child who knows this subject well will grow up smart, broad-minded and successfully work in any field, - says our President Sh. Mirziyoyev, who also firmly believes in this science.

Indeed, mathematics is considered the king of the sciences. This article also contains simple questions that are necessary in everyday life. Students in grades 1-4 should be able to add up the prices of cheap goods at home or in a store and calculate their price. A person who knows mathematics will never make mistakes in calculations, he knows how much money he has and, most importantly, knows how to think when to spend it.

At present, one of the main tasks of teaching mathematics in primary schools is to educate students in all respects as mature people. At the same time, it is important to provide them with knowledge in mathematics, to ensure the validity and thoroughness of the knowledge they study, to form the skills and abilities to apply them. In particular, the main tasks of primary mathematical education should be the development of mental abilities in mathematics classes and the formation of the necessary skills and competencies for the successful use of the acquired knowledge in conscious life in the future.

Solving mathematical problems is an important component of teaching mathematics. It is impossible to imagine mastering mathematics without solving problems. In mathematics, the theory of problem solving is an important way to apply it in practice. Problem solving is important in the process of assimilation of one or another theoretical material studied in the primary grades, and plays an important role in the development of the mental abilities of students. Tasks are created on the basis of a system of practical cases. This means that the compilation of each new concept is always carried out by solving a particular problem that helps to explain the meaning of this concept and requires its application. Work on the release begins with the development of its content. If the condition of the problem is confusing, it is appropriate to give students one to three minutes to think about the content of the problem on their own. Let's pay attention to the analysis of the problems given in the mathematics textbook for grade 4. In the mathematics textbook for grade 4, much attention is paid to the ability to write, read and apply numbers.

1. 1200 loaves of bread delivered to the store. Three times less than the bread brought before noon, the remaining bread was sold in the afternoon. How much bread was sold during the day?

The:

Bread - 1200 pcs.

Sold - 3 times less

Find: How many loaves of bread were sold in a day

Solution: 1) $1200:3=400$ 2) $1200-400=800$

Answer: 800

2. The book consists of 24 pages. If you read 4 pages every day, how many days can you read. How about reading 2 pages every day?

The:

Book - 24 pages

Need to find: How many days to finish after reading from 4 and 2 pages?

Solution: 1) $24:4=6$ 2) $24:2=12$

Answer: 6 versus 12 days.

3. On the first day of the road construction, 620 tons of sand were brought, on the second day 197 tons less than on the first day, and on the third day 86 tons less than on the second day. How many tons of sand were brought on the third day?

The:

1 day - 620 t

On the 2nd day - 197 tons less than on the 1st day

On the 3rd day - 86 tons less than on the 2nd day

Need to find: How many tons of sand were brought on the third day?

Decision: 1) $620-197=423$ 2) $423-86=337$

Answer: 337 tons of sand were supplied.

4. According to the plan, the factory should sew 350 coats in 10 days. Factory workers covered 2 coats more than planned per day. How many coats did the factory make in 10 days?

The:

Coat - 350 pcs.

More than 2 layers per day

Must be found; How many coats did the factory make in 10 days?

Solution: 1) $350:10=35$ 2) $35+2=37$ 3) $37*10=370$

Answer: 370 coats.

Summary:In conclusion, in order to use the possibilities of innovative methods in the formation of logical thinking in elementary school lessons, the essence and content of each concept and its justification on the practical experience of students, as well as the widespread introduction of clarity, comparison, drawing conclusions, in general, is the basis for creating such patterns. In other actions based on comparison and analysis of exercises and examples, work on mistakes and effective use of all this.

In the process of solving the problem, the problem is fully explained to students and connected with life. The purpose of this is to get an idea of the problem in the minds of the students. We will also go to the world of fairy tales to keep

students interested while solving the problem..Only these methods can increase the student's interest in science. This is a great achievement for a teacher.

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